

Bayesian verification of an energy conservation measure

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Abstract

Most building owners eventually invest in energy conservation measures for their buildings. Faced with a variety of options, ranging from trivial (replacing light bulbs) to major (better façade insulation), they want to know which measure will yield the highest return on investment—and with what confidence. Moreover, once the measure has been applied, they will want to know how well it performs and whether their money was well spent—also known as Measurement & Verification (M&V).

But conventional M&V mandates the establishment of a baseline. The building should be instrumented during a year or more before applying the measure, driving the costs of M&V to sometimes unacceptable levels. Furthermore, a typical M&V study will report a single number for the measure’s efficiency, ignoring any uncertainty surrounding that estimate.

To solve these two problems (expensive baseline and absence of uncertainty), we have developed a method, based on Bayesian statistics, that will 1) rely on historic utility bills and climate data to establish the baseline, and 2) estimate, with confidence intervals, how effective the energy conservation measure was.

We have tested this method after installing, in March 2016, a model-predictive controller for space heating for a medium-sized (about 2700 m²) office building in Switzerland. The baseline was established from historic oil tank refill records and climate data from a nearby weather station. The total heat loss coefficient of the building was assessed 46 days after the installation and found to have decreased by 31.9 %, with 17.8 percentage points standard error.

Keywords: Bayesian inference, heating degree days, base temperature, balance point temperature, total heat loss coefficient

1. Introduction

Many energy conservation measures (ECMs) can reduce the energy consumption of existing buildings, but they vary widely in cost and effectiveness. Faced with a variety of options, ranging from trivial (replacing light bulbs) to major (better façade insulation), building owners need to know which measure is likely to yield the highest return on investment—and with what confidence. Moreover, once the measure has been applied, the owner needs to know how well it performs and whether their money was well spent—an activity known as Measurement & Verification (M&V).

This is a growing problem for Swiss firms that have publicly committed to reducing their greenhouse gas emissions. The majority of these emissions can be traced to large portfolios of legacy buildings [1], in particular to the fossil fuels used for heating. Reducing the heating energy for legacy buildings (while maintaining user comfort) can help such companies achieve their objectives—provided those energy savings can be proven. This is frequently a stumbling block for building managers who may prefer spending their budget on traditional (but perhaps less

effective) energy conservation projects, and avoid riskier (but more effective) solutions.

Proving the effectiveness of any ECM is hard. Many factors influence the energy consumption of a building, and must be accounted for before and after the installation. Proper M&V typically involves establishing a “baseline” model of the building’s energy consumption, ideally covering at least one year. After the installation, the energy consumption is measured again and compared with the prediction from the baseline model, yielding the energy savings. But in our experience, it would appear that many M&V projects ignore the uncertainties surrounding the baseline model and report a point estimate for the energy savings, giving a false sense of accuracy.

Lack of confidence in the effectiveness of ECMs hinders their adoption [2]. To convince building owners to undertake more ECM projects we must address three concerns: 1) the risk that the ECM might not be as effective as advertised, 2) the risk that, although effective, the benefits will turn out to be difficult to prove, and 3) the risk of a poor return on investment. The latter depends not only on the effectiveness of the ECM, but also on the fluctuating energy prices throughout the lifetime of the building, as discussed by Kumbaroglu and Madlener [3]. Mitigating risks 1) and 2) is the goal of M&V, currently perceived

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as “an inaccurate science: an engineering practice relying heavily on professional judgement” [4]. We must show building owners that assessing the effectiveness of an ECM can become an almost mechanical process, one that yields not just the estimated energy savings but also their accuracy, while complying with existing international norms.

1.1. The International Performance Measurement and Verification Protocol

The International Performance Measurement and Verification Protocol (IPMVP) [5] is a widely recognized framework for conducting M&V projects. It provides a set of guidelines and defines common terms for such projects. Energy savings are determined by first establishing a model of the building’s baseline energy demand. After the installation, the energy demand is measured again during a so-called reporting period. Energy savings are calculated from the difference between the baseline and reporting periods, taking into account external factors that influence the demand:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Savings} &= \text{Baseline period demand} \\ &\quad - \text{Reporting period demand} \\ &\quad \pm \text{Adjustments} \end{aligned}$$

The IPMVP leaves no doubt on the need for quantifiable uncertainties:

In order to communicate savings in a statistically valid manner, savings need to be expressed along with their associated confidence and precision levels. [5, p. 88]

Indeed the whole point of M&V projects is to *reliably* determine energy savings. Although the definition of “reliably” rests ultimately on the user of the M&V report, the IPMVP suggests that savings, to be statistically significant, should be at least twice the standard error of the baseline energy consumption [5, p. 88]. The IPMVP is otherwise silent on the methods by which the uncertainties are to be estimated.

1.2. Recent assessments

To see how such projects are carried out in a laboratory setting, we performed a Scopus search for documents containing “IPMVP” in their title, abstract, or keywords, limiting the search to publication dates after 2010. This yields 37 documents, of which just 3 study the energy efficiency of an ECM without resorting to computer simulation:

- The retrofit of a water cooling package unit, whose baseline consumption from July 2012 to June 2013 was modeled as a linear combination of occupancy, number of working days and cooling degree days. The reporting period ran from August 2013 to July 2014, and a *t*-test determined whether the energy

savings were significant. Very different results were obtained depending on which variables were used to model the baseline energy consumption, and the relative uncertainty on the energy savings ranged from 86% to 232% [6].

- Two near-identical 300-seat conference rooms retrofitted with a variable-flow air-handling unit. The energy savings were determined by simulation and by retrofitting one room while leaving the other unchanged. Both approaches yielded roughly 30% energy savings on the heating coil’s consumption, but the simulation grossly underestimated the savings on the fans’ electrical consumption [7].
- A large-scale government-sponsored program offering rebates to home owners for increasing the energy efficiency of new and existing homes by at least 30%. Nearly 12 000 households participated during the 6 years of the program. The IPMVP protocol was applied to a sample of 52 households. The baseline was established as a linear model in heating degree days, cooling degree days, relative humidity, and energy price. An average of 172 kWh annual energy savings was found, with monetary annual savings ranging from -\$515 to \$530 [8].

Other examples of retrofit assessments found in the literature include:

- An analysis of 32 retrofit projects, ranging in size from three to 30 000 houses, in order to rank the cost-effectiveness of different energy conservation measures. The space heating energy was normalized to a fixed base temperature of 18.3°C. The project used a mix of submetered data and utility bills [9].
- A high-tech, 31 000 m² campus in California whose HVAC equipment was retrofitted. The baseline period ran from September 2007 to August 2008, and the reporting period from May 2009 to April 2010. The energy consumption was normalised to the outdoor temperature, and the annual electricity consumption was reduced by 3 853 625 kWh, although no uncertainty was reported for this extraordinarily precise figure [10].
- An analysis of the electric load of 17 office buildings, modeled as a piecewise linear function of time of week and outdoor temperature. Cross-validation was used to estimate the uncertainty in the baseline: the last month of baseline data was excluded from the model, and compared with the model’s prediction. The difference is an estimate of the model’s uncertainties [11].

This short review suggests that even in an academic setting, the uncertainty on energy savings are frequently highly dependent on the model [6], assume an arbitrary base

temperature for heating degree days calculation [8, 9], or are ignored [7, 10]. Walter et al. [11] have proposed a method that is a step towards making energy savings uncertainty estimation more reliable, but they concede that the method is limited by the amount of data available.

In this paper we describe a method based on Bayesian data analysis, which we believe yields correct uncertainties no matter how much data is available.

1.3. Present study

Swisscom, a leading Swiss telecommunications company, owns and operates about 1300 buildings in Switzerland, of which about 950 are sales, office, and non-production buildings. They are one of the largest building owners in Switzerland in number of buildings. The yearly energy bill for their buildings is estimated at CHF 70 million. They are publicly committed to “save double the amount of CO₂ generated by [their] entire operations and supply chain” for themselves and their customers by 2020, and to “increase [their] own energy efficiency by a further 35% between 2016 and 2020” [12]. Like many major Swiss companies, their stock of buildings is dominated by heating systems using non-renewable fuels. Energy conservation measures that would make these buildings more efficient are particularly attractive. In late 2015, a pilot study was chartered to evaluate the effectiveness of model-predictive control for space heating.

A commercial adaptive model-predictive controller based on artificial neural networks called NOL^a (Neurobat On-Line—analogue) [13] was chosen for a building in Sargans, a Swiss locality in the canton of St. Gallen. Like many buildings, the pre-installation energy efficiency of this building was not well understood by the building’s owner, and the project plan did not allow for the measurement of a baseline. All that was available was a record of oil tank refills, dating back to 2011. The poor baseline data made Bayesian methods, which maximize the use of available information, particularly attractive for this project.

We first describe the test installation in section 2, followed by a review in section 3 of the Bayesian data analysis method used to establish the building’s performance before and after the installation. The weather, baseline period data, and reporting period data will be analysed in section 4, and we will draw inferences about the effectiveness of the controller in section 5.

2. Pilot building

The Sargans building shown in Fig. 1 features four heating circuits, covering about 2700 m², with heating water provided by an oil-fired boiler. The NOL^a system was installed in March 2016, covering three of the four circuits. The fourth circuit was deemed not to require optimisation, as the zone in question is kept relatively cool. The total surface covered by NOL^a is about 1840 m².

The oil-fired boiler draws its fuel from two tanks and provides the heating water to all heating circuits. The

Figure 1: Aerial (top left) and side views of the Altbau (bottom) and Neubau (right) parts of the Sargans building.

levels in the tanks are recorded at irregular intervals, such as when either tank is refilled. The domestic hot water is provided by an independent electrical circuit.

The NOL^a system is a model-predictive controller that regularly computes an optimal water supply temperature. It belongs to the ECM category of “Energy efficient equipment and low energy technologies”, a form of demand side management [2]. The optimal temperature cannot be communicated directly to most legacy heating controllers; instead, the NOL^a system controls the supply temperature indirectly by shifting the outdoor temperature measured by the existing heating controller. Thus, the boiler provides heating water for each circuit at just the right temperature for that circuit. The details of the NOL^a algorithms are beyond the scope of this article but can be found elsewhere [14–20].

The installation of the NOL^a system included an oil meter that could be read out automatically. All sensors attached to the NOL^a system (including the oil meter) were automatically sampled several times per hour and stored in a database. The data is used for monitoring, preventive maintenance, and offline analysis.

3. Modelling the building’s heating demand

To verify the effectiveness of the new heating control system, we need to establish two models for the building’s heating energy demand: one before the installation, one after. Both models will have the same structure, but different parameters. The parameters must be estimated from the available data: the model before the installation will be estimated from the oil fill records, while the model after the installation will be estimated from the automated oil meter readouts. We begin by defining the structure of the model, and then we discuss how the parameters can be estimated from the data.

3.1. Heating energy model

A building’s heating energy demand is rarely constant but varies over time due to so-called routine factors (expected to vary, such as the climate) and non-routine factors (normally constant, such as the indoor temperature set point or the activity inside the building).

Under normal conditions, when the indoor temperature follows a desired set point, the daily heating energy demand of a building will balance the heat losses. The heat losses on a given day will, intuitively, be larger on colder days than on warmer days. Some days will be so warm that no heating is required, all heat losses being compensated by the sun and other free gains; the outdoor temperature above which this happens (called the building’s *base temperature* θ_b) is usually taken to be equal to the indoor temperature set point up to a constant offset. We should also allow for day-to-day random fluctuations in the heating demand, which we will model by Gaussian noise $\mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2)$ of mean 0 and whose variance σ^2 will have to be estimated. Such models have been called *probabilistic semi-physical models* in some papers [21].

(This assumes that the variance of the daily heating energy demand is constant, which is never true: above the base temperature, the daily heating energy demand will be stabler than below the base temperature. But we do not believe the model needs this extra complexity.)

Putting it all together, the daily losses Q_d on a day d are proportional to the positive difference between the average outdoor temperature $\overline{\theta_{out d}}$ and the building’s base temperature θ_b , plus random noise:

$$Q_d = K \times (\theta_b - \overline{\theta_{out d}})^+ + \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2), \quad (1)$$

where the constant of proportionality K , called the building’s *total heat loss coefficient*, is the quantity of extra heat required per day to maintain indoor comfort for each extra degree of cold. $\mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2)$ stands for Gaussian noise of mean 0 and variance σ^2 . We agreed with the customer that the effectiveness of the new heating control system would be determined from changes to K , since the base temperature θ_b might change if the indoor temperature set point is not the same before and after the installation.

Over a period p made up of n_p days, the total heating load will be

$$Q_p = \sum_{d \in p} Q_d = K \times DD_p + \mathcal{N}(0, n_p \sigma^2), \quad (2)$$

where $DD_p = \sum_{d \in p} (\theta_b - \overline{\theta_{out d}})^+$ is the number of *degree-days at base temperature* θ_b during that period. The load Q_p and the period duration n_p are directly read from utility bills or energy meter readouts, while DD_p must be calculated from historic weather data and the building’s estimated base temperature.

Our task is to estimate the total heat loss coefficient K , the base temperature θ_b , and the daily fluctuations σ from the data. None of them can be estimated independently

of the others; underestimating θ_b will lead to an overestimate of K and vice-versa. It is a serious mistake to use a “one size fits all” base temperature, in spite of current recommendations by building regulations and policies. A recent example of this was shown by an analysis of gas meter data on 119 buildings by Meng and Mourshed [22]; they applied an algorithm due to Paulus [23] and found base temperatures ranging from 11.6°C to 20.5°C, while the “standard” base temperature in the UK is 15.5°C [24].

3.2. Bayesian estimation

The set of utility bills (or energy meters readouts) $\{Q_p, n_p\}$ constitutes the data we have at hand, while Eq. (2) is a probability model from which that data is drawn. Bayesian inference consists in finding the parameters of that probability model that are the most consistent with the observed data, or more precisely finding the *probability density functions* (pdf) of these parameters [25].

Let D stand for the set of reporting periods (for example, a set of monthly gas utility bills, or a list of oil tank level readouts) and historic weather data. Bayesian inference consists in establishing the probability density function for the parameters $\{K, \theta_b, \sigma\}$ conditioned on the information D , noted as $p(\{K, \theta_b, \sigma\} | D)$. A method to do so has been described by Lindelöf [26] and implemented in a package for the R programming environment [27]. But unlike that prior work, which focused on the determination of a building’s base temperature, here we will perform this estimation twice (before and after the installation), and be interested in the change to the building’s heat loss coefficient K .

We assume that installing an ECM such as the NOL^a will alter the building’s total heat loss coefficient by a factor ρ , and also possibly shift the base temperature if the indoor temperature set point is not exactly identical before and after the installation:

$$K_{pre} \rightarrow K_{post} = \rho \times K_{pre}$$

$$\theta_{b,pre} \rightarrow \theta_{b,post} = \theta_{b,pre} + \Delta\theta_b$$

A shift in the building’s base temperature θ_b should not trouble us, since very little was known about the indoor temperature set point before the retrofit. It was therefore agreed that the effectiveness of the ECM would be quantified by the ratio ρ between the post- and pre-installation heat loss coefficients K . The lower ρ is, the more effective is the new control system. The relative energy savings in percent (ignoring changes to θ_b) are then given by $100 \times (1 - \rho)$; if, for example, K would miraculously become 0, we would have 100% energy savings.

Strict Bayesians would now write a full probability model involving all the pre- and post-installation model parameters, work out the joint posterior probability density function, draw samples from that function and make inferences. That would be correct, but the problem can be considerably simplified by noting that the pre- and post-installation parameters are conditionally independent; the

pre-installation parameters $\{K_{\text{pre}}, \theta_{\text{b,pre}}, \sigma_{\text{pre}}\}$ are independent of their post-installation counterparts. Furthermore, the likelihood of the pre-installation data D_{pre} is independent of the post-installation parameters, and vice-versa. In effect, we are dealing with two independent experiments: one before the installation, and one after. The pre- and post-installation parameters' probability distribution functions can, without loss of information, be derived independently.

(One could argue that the measurement noise σ should *not* be independent; in fact, it would be reasonable to consider them as the same before and after the installation. But that would be true only if the energy consumption was recorded in the same way before and after; σ expresses not only the daily inherent variability in energy consumption of the building, but also includes measurement errors. Since the oil consumption was measured with two completely different methods before and after the installation, we must treat σ_{pre} and σ_{post} as two independent parameters.)

Putting it together formally, the task consists in establishing $p(\{K_{\text{pre}}, \theta_{\text{b,pre}}, \sigma_{\text{pre}}, K_{\text{post}}, \theta_{\text{b,post}}, \sigma_{\text{post}}\} | D)$ where D now stands for the union of the pre- and post-installation data D_{pre} and D_{post} . Since we assume conditional independence between the parameters before and after the retrofit, we have

$$\begin{aligned} p(\{K_{\text{pre}}, \theta_{\text{b,pre}}, \sigma_{\text{pre}}, K_{\text{post}}, \theta_{\text{b,post}}, \sigma_{\text{post}}\} | D) &= p(\{K_{\text{pre}}, \theta_{\text{b,pre}}, \sigma_{\text{pre}}\} | D) \\ &\quad \times p(\{K_{\text{post}}, \theta_{\text{b,post}}, \sigma_{\text{post}}\} | D) \\ &= p(\{K_{\text{pre}}, \theta_{\text{b,pre}}, \sigma_{\text{pre}}\} | D_{\text{pre}}) \\ &\quad \times p(\{K_{\text{post}}, \theta_{\text{b,post}}, \sigma_{\text{post}}\} | D_{\text{post}}) \end{aligned}$$

where each term in the product on the right-hand side can be computed by the method proposed by Lindelöf [26]. The second equality holds because the post-installation parameters do not depend on the pre-installation data, and vice-versa. Once we have the probability density function on the left-hand side of the equation, we can draw random pairs of $\{K_{\text{pre}}, K_{\text{post}}\}$ values from it and make inferences about $\rho = K_{\text{post}}/K_{\text{pre}}$.

A fully Bayesian approach like the one just described is mathematically straightforward. Perhaps its only drawback is its computational cost, but excellent algorithms exist to make this process highly efficient. We have reasons to believe that only a fully Bayesian approach will maximize the information contained in the data, which is a desirable trait when dealing with high quality data but an essential one when dealing with incomplete or inaccurate data.

Perhaps more significantly, it would also appear that only Bayesian methods are free from certain arbitrary assumptions commonly encountered in classical statistics. For example, most linear regression problems minimize the squared error between the observed and the fitted data. But why minimize the squared error, and not, say, the

absolute error? It turns out that this choice depends on how errors are modelled, and Bayesian linear regression methods make this dependency explicit.

There are other methods for estimating the parameters of such models. The performance line method of Day et al. [28] is frequently used for estimating the base temperature when daily data is not available. The method consists in plotting the energy against the degree-days for a given base temperature, and fitting a second order polynomial. The base temperature is then adjusted until the second order coefficient of that polynomial vanishes. This method yields good results, but this choice of finding a base temperature such that the relationship between energy and degree-days becomes linear seems to us, again, rather arbitrary.

We have also seen practitioners use variants of the performance line method: maximizing the coefficient of determination R^2 ; making the intercept vanish; or minimizing the sum of unweighted squared residuals. Again, all these non-Bayesian methods suffer from arbitrary assumptions. It seems to us that the most credible alternative to a fully Bayesian approach is a non-linear regression approach, described below.

We should also mention that Bayesian methods have recently been employed by Chong et al. [29] and Heine et al. [30] to infer other kinds of building parameters from measurements; perhaps the only flaw in their approach is their choice of prior distribution, which tended to remain unaffected by the data. It would perhaps have been better to start with uninformative priors.

3.3. Non-linear regression

To the best of our knowledge, the best classical approach for estimating the parameters of our model is non-linear regression, which we will compare to a fully Bayesian method.

In non-linear regression we search for the set of parameters $\{K, \theta_{\text{b}}\}$ that minimizes the sum of weighted squared residuals

$$\sum_p (Q_p - K \times DD_p)^2 / n_p. \quad (3)$$

The $1/n_p$ weights are proportional to the inverse variance of the energy demand of each period p : intuitively, we normalize the noise of each period's energy demand by the number of days in that period. But notice that the daily fluctuations σ do not enter this sum. They must be estimated from the sample variance of the residuals.

Minimizing this sum of weighted squared residuals can be handled by off-the-shelf function optimization routines, which will find the "best" estimate of the $\{K, \theta_{\text{b}}\}$ parameters. Most solvers will also evaluate the Hessian of the objective function around its minimum, approximating it with a quadratic function of the parameters, and use the curvature of that approximation to estimate the uncertainty on the parameters. This is indeed what was done by Lindelöf [26] in a first attempt at estimating the parameters of a building by Bayesian methods, although he did

not minimize the sum of weighted squared residuals but maximized a quantity called the likelihood (which, unlike the sum (3), includes the daily fluctuations σ).

4. Data analysis

Unlike traditional IPMVP projects, this pilot building is challenging because daily oil consumption readouts from an oil meter were available only after the installation of the NOL^a. The energy savings must therefore be derived from different sources: manual oil level readouts before the installation, and automated daily oil readouts after. In both cases, they must be correlated with the weather data so we look at that first.

4.1. Weather data

The historic weather data (dating from 2011) is obtained from MétéoSuisse [31], who provides a file with average daily temperatures measured in Bad Ragaz (about 6 km from Sargans) and Vaduz (about 10 km). The relative positions of the pilot building in Sargans and of the Bad Ragaz and Vaduz weather stations are shown on the map in Fig. 2. The Bad Ragaz data is shown against time in Fig. 3. A scatterplot of the temperatures from Bad Ragaz against those from Vaduz is shown in Fig. 4. Since there are no obvious differences between the two weather stations we use from now on the data from Bad Ragaz. Sargans lies 483 m above sea level, Bad Ragaz 496 m, so we do not adjust the outdoor temperature for altitude.

4.2. Baseline oil consumption

The historic oil consumption data consists in a sheet of paper used to log the readouts of the oil levels in the boiler's tanks. A copy of the original paper is shown in Fig. 8 in the Appendix. A transcribed version is shown in Table 1.

There are log entries (for example on 2 May 2012) when one tank was filled without recording its level before the refill. In such instances it is impossible to know how much oil was used during the preceding period. We therefore restrict this data to the 12 periods during which neither tank level increased, for example between 2011-02-03 and 2011-05-25 (2300 L of oil) but not between 2011-10-25 and 2011-11-25 (no readout for the second tank) nor between 2015-03-25 and 2015-06-10 (both tanks increased).

Each period is matched with its historic weather data, yielding for each period a list of mean daily outdoor temperatures with one datum for each day of the period. We obtain the data shown in Table 2.

Note that two records in the oil readouts are probably erroneous and should be excluded from the analysis:

1. From 2013-03-06 to 2013-06-17 (103 days): 200 L, or about 2 L per day (far too little)
2. From 2013-06-17 to 2013-08-15 (59 days): 5500 L, or about 100 L per day during summer (far too much)

Figure 2: Sargans region, including the Bad Ragaz and Vaduz weather stations.

Figure 3: Historic outdoor temperatures measured at Bad Ragaz.

Figure 4: Comparison between Bad Ragaz and Vaduz temperatures.

The building’s base temperature and heat loss coefficient are estimated from this data. The Bayesian approach yields

$$\theta_{b,\text{pre}} = 17.4 \pm 1.9^\circ\text{C}, \quad K_{\text{pre}} = 6.1 \pm 1.3 \text{ L/Kd},$$

while a non-linear regression yields

$$\theta_{b,\text{pre}} = 17.4 \pm 2.3^\circ\text{C}, \quad K_{\text{pre}} = 6.1 \pm 1.6 \text{ L/Kd}.$$

Both approaches yield comparable results, but there is one important difference: the Bayesian approach provides a posterior pdf for each parameter, which in turn makes it possible to compute a posterior pdf for quantities derived from these parameters. In particular, we will later have to calculate the pdf of $K_{\text{post}}/K_{\text{pre}}$; this cannot be done easily with the point estimates provided by the non-linear regression.

Now that we have the building’s base temperature, we can validate it by calculating the number of degree days for each oil consumption period and plotting the oil consumed during each period against the degree days of that period. If the base temperature is correct, we should obtain points lying on a straight line that goes through the origin. We show this in Fig. 5, where for comparison we do the same with degree days calculated with non-linear regression and using different official standards [24, 32]. The Bayesian method yields the best results. The relationship between the oil consumption and the degree days using the estimated base temperature is satisfactorily linear, with the exception of the two outliers identified above, and possibly a third point with 2300 L of oil for about 750 degree days.

Date	Tank1	Tank2	Total
2011-02-03	7500	13300	20800
2011-05-25	5500	13000	18500
2011-10-25	4000	13000	17000
2011-11-25	10700		
2012-02-23	10500	3300	13800
2012-04-10	10000	500	10500
2012-05-02		11100	
2012-05-27	8000	10500	18500
2013-01-15	10000	10300	20300
2013-03-06	10000	5200	15200
2013-06-17	10000	5000	15000
2013-08-15	9500	0	9500
2013-08-15	13450	12500	25950
2013-11-27	13437	8800	22237
2014-07-25	9500	500	10000
2014-09-24	9000	500	9500
2014-09-24	9000	12500	21500
2014-11-18	7000	12500	19500
2014-11-18	9100	12500	21600
2014-12-03	7400	12500	19900
2015-02-10		12400	
2015-03-25	0	7500	7500
2015-06-10	13200	10000	23200
2015-12-15	13200	3500	16700
2016-03-08	8500		

Table 1: Transcribed oil level readouts, grouped by year.

4.3. Reporting period

The new control system included an oil counter that could be read out automatically. With this data we could correlate the oil consumption with the outdoor temperature on a daily basis, instead of having to wait until the next oil tank refill. That relationship is shown in Fig. 6.

Each point in this plot represents one day between 1 April 2016, when a mislabeling of the existing heating system was identified and corrected, and 16 May 2016, just before the end of the heating season. The post-installation total heat loss coefficient K_{post} could also be obtained by fitting a straight line through these points, since each point represents one day of oil consumption and they are all below the base temperature. But we keep our Bayesian approach, which yields

$$\theta_{b,\text{post}} = 20.3 \pm 0.7^\circ\text{C} \quad K_{\text{post}} = 4.5 \pm 0.3 \text{ L/Kd},$$

while the non-linear regression yields

$$\theta_{b,\text{post}} = 20.3 \pm 0.8^\circ\text{C} \quad K_{\text{post}} = 4.5 \pm 0.3 \text{ L/Kd}.$$

Again, both approaches are practically equivalent, and they both find a post-installation heat loss coefficient about

Figure 5: Oil consumption vs heating degree days, calculated with different base temperatures as follows. Bayesian: calculated from the data as described in the main text; ASHRAE: 65 °F (18.3 °C) as recommended by the ASHRAE Handbook [32]; SIA 380:2015: 12 °C, the standard used in Switzerland; Carbon Trust: 15.5 °C, the standard used in the UK [24]; SIA 381/3: a retired Swiss norm, where the base temperature is 20 °C but only for those days whose average temperature is below 12 °C. Unfilled circles indicate the two records that have been excluded from the analysis. The heat loss coefficient K is given in L/Kd. The Bayesian base temperature yields the highest coefficient of determination R^2 , suggesting that it fits the data best.

From	To	Days	Oil (L)	Avg. daily cons. (L)	Avg. temp. (°C)
2011-02-03	2011-05-25	111	2300	20.7	10.1
2011-05-25	2011-10-25	153	1500	9.8	16.9
2012-02-23	2012-04-10	47	3300	70.2	8.2
2013-01-15	2013-03-06	50	5100	102.0	0.2
2013-03-06	2013-06-17	103	200	1.9	10.5
2013-06-17	2013-08-15	59	5500	93.2	19.8
2013-08-15	2013-11-27	104	3713	35.7	12.1
2013-11-27	2014-07-25	240	12 237	51.0	9.9
2014-07-25	2014-09-24	61	500	8.2	16.5
2014-09-24	2014-11-18	55	2000	36.4	12.0
2014-11-18	2014-12-03	15	1700	113.3	6.9
2015-06-10	2015-12-15	188	6500	34.6	14.2

Table 2: Usable pre-installation consumption periods. The building’s average energy demand is about 207 720 kWh/a according to the building manager, which would be about 56 L/d of oil on average assuming a heat content of 10.08 kWh/L.

30% smaller than before the installation. Notice also how daily meter readouts improve the precision of the parameter estimation compared with historic oil fill records.

5. Results

The effect on the building’s heat loss coefficient, defined as $\rho = K_{\text{post}}/K_{\text{pre}}$, can now be evaluated. From a Bayesian point of view, ρ is a function of two random variables K_{pre} and K_{post} and we need its probability distribution function. This can be estimated by drawing randomly from the joint pdfs of K_{pre} and K_{post} , calculating ρ (or rather, $1 - \rho$), and evaluating values of interest such as the mean value, standard deviation, and so on.

A histogram of 20 000 values drawn for $1 - \rho$ is shown in Fig. 7. The majority of that histogram is positive, indicating a decrease in the heat loss coefficient. Any statement about the energy savings can now be made with its associated confidence. For example, 75% of the mass of this histogram lies to the right of 0.14; this can be reported to decision makers by saying that the heat loss coefficient has been reduced by at least 14% with 75% confidence.

But this distribution clearly does not follow a normal distribution, so it would be misleading to merely report the distribution’s mean and standard deviation. The ‘best’ estimate of the effect is obtained instead by finding the narrowest range of $1 - \rho$ values such that they encompass $N\%$ of the mass of the histogram, also known as the $N\%$ credible interval, for any desired N . Since one standard error of a normal distribution corresponds to a 67% credible interval, we agreed with the building owner that the uncertainty on the effect should be reported with $N = 67$. We obtain:

$$\text{Reduction of heat losses (\%)} = 28.4 \pm 17.3,$$

where the \pm sign is understood to represent the 67% credible interval.

What would we have done differently if we had estimated the building parameters with non-linear regression?

Figure 6: Daily oil consumption vs daily average outdoor temperatures. A linear fit is shown with its confidence bands. A second order coefficient was not statistically significant ($p = 0.198$).

We have point estimates of the total heat loss coefficients before and after the installation, together with their standard error. But we don't know their distribution (since a non-linear regression does not yield pdfs), so we are forced to assume Gaussian distributions. The ratio of two Gaussian random variables has a complex, but closed form, and the probability density computed by this closed form, using the moments provided by the non-linear regression, is shown as a solid line on Fig. 7. If the two approaches agreed, the solid line would roughly go through the top center of each bar of the histogram. Here they disagree somewhat: the non-linear regression is slightly shifted to the left, towards negative values. The non-linear regression approach would therefore tend to underestimate the effect on the heat loss coefficient.

6. Discussion

We have estimated the reduction of heat losses caused by the installation of a new heating control system and reported that effect in a form familiar to decision makers: a point estimate \pm an uncertainty. This form is sufficient for most building owners, provided that pains are taken to clearly explain how the uncertainty should be interpreted.

In our case we have reported an uncertainty of 17.3 percentage points, which may sound large and it is tempting to try and reduce that error by letting the experiment run longer. But doing so will only reduce the error on the post-installation heat loss coefficient K_{post} ; there is nothing we can do about the error on the pre-installation heat loss coefficient K_{pre} , which dominates the total error. The absolute error on ρ has a lower limit given by the relative error on K_{pre} : $\Delta\rho \geq \rho \times \Delta K_{\text{pre}} / K_{\text{pre}}$. In our case, $\rho = 0.7$, $\Delta K_{\text{pre}} = 1.3$, $K_{\text{pre}} = 6.1$ and therefore $\Delta\rho \geq 0.15$, very close to the current uncertainty of 17.3 percentage points. After 46 days, our accuracy is almost as good as it will ever get.

The magnitude of the effect is less than twice its uncertainty, so a strict interpretation of the IPMVP text would deem it not statistically significant. But Fig. 7 makes it clear that the effect is more likely to be positive than not. A single point estimate with its uncertainty cannot convey all the information that has been drawn from the data. On the other hand, inflicting probability density functions on decision makers is probably not wiser. Instead, we have quite successfully used this pdf to answer typical questions raised by users, such as “What are the most likely energy savings?”, “What energy savings can I expect on average?”, or “How likely am I to achieve energy savings of at least 20%?”. All these questions can be answered with the probability distribution function.

The following caveats should, however, be kept in mind:

- We have taken the reduction of the heat loss coefficient K as being synonymous with energy savings; this is only correct for a constant base temperature. In particular, shifts in the indoor temperature set

Figure 7: Probability density distribution of the heat loss reduction $1 - \rho$.

point can equally well mitigate or magnify those energy savings.

- We have assumed that the building's base temperature and heat loss coefficient have remained constant during 2011–2015.
- We have assumed that a linear relationship holds between the oil consumption and the average outdoor temperature post-installation, but Fig. 6 suggests a good deal of variance that must be attributed to other factors than the outdoor temperature, perhaps the solar irradiance.
- Fig. 6 also suggests that the building's base temperature may have shifted upwards after the installation of the NOL^a system. This happens when the temperature set point programmed on the NOL^a is higher than the average temperature kept by the original heating system. But historic indoor temperatures are rarely available, and the NOL^a installer relied on the temperature set point programmed on the original heating system—which can be very different from the temperature really desired by the user. This does not invalidate the above analysis, but the building manager should consider adjusting those set points to fully reap the energy savings.

None of these caveats are specific to the Bayesian approach, and apply to many (or most) ECM projects. However, they do not seem to be frequently discussed. We suppose that traditional methods might make it easier for unwarranted assumptions to go undetected, and we can only

recommend that the final users of ECM projects should challenge any assumptions made.

Finally, it should be noted that our approach was focused on reducing the heating energy demand of a building. But there are many energy conservation measures whose purpose is to reduce other forms of energy: cooling loads and artificial lighting are two obvious examples. A Bayesian approach similar to the one presented here can deal with such situations, provided a suitable model is developed.

7. Conclusion

7.1. Summary of results

Upgrading the heating control system of the building in Sargans has lowered the total heat loss coefficient of that building by 28.4 ± 17.3 %. This estimate was obtained by fitting a probability model to the pre- and post-installation oil consumption data. The parameters of that model include the building's total heat loss coefficient and its base temperature, both before and after the installation. This yielded a probability density function in all the building's parameters, from which the effect on the heat loss coefficient was estimated.

We have used a Bayesian analysis framework throughout this analysis and compared it with a more classical counterpart (a non-linear regression approach). Both approaches were able to:

- handle a complex probability model, such as the one relating the daily energy consumption to the mean outdoor temperature
- take into account data from very different sources (pre-installation manual entries and post-installation automated daily readouts)
- estimate the pre- and post-installation building model parameters

The Bayesian approach had the following advantages over its counterpart:

- the clear interpretability and communicability of its results
- easier to program (for the non-linear regression analysis, we had to work around certain limitations in the packages provided by R)
- fewer ad-hoc assumptions

Since this is a case study on a real building (with unknown “real” parameters) we cannot judge which method is more accurate. But because of its simplicity, ease of programming, and lack of arbitrary assumptions, our preference goes to the Bayesian method, with which we were able to avoid a costly pre-installation period of measurements. The owner of the building was aware that the precision of

the energy savings was going to be limited by the accuracy of the pre-installation manual readouts, and appreciated the efforts made to communicate the results to decision-makers.

Not all buildings will enjoy the luxury of automated energy consumption readouts, and it is likely that future projects will have no choice but to rely on manual readouts both before and after the installation. The Bayesian framework will be able to handle these situations, but with an interesting twist: it will probably be possible to pool the pre- and post-installation data to better estimate the daily energy consumption variability σ , which we did not do here because the data acquisition methods were completely different.

Another vexing point concerns the apparent shift in the building's base temperature. Some shift is probably inevitable due to a change in the average indoor temperature, but can the entire shift be entirely attributed to the indoor temperature alone? Or is there something inherent in the new control system that also shifts that base temperature? This too remains an interesting open question.

7.2. Recommendations

Throughout this work we have tried to satisfy two classes of readers: the academics, who wish to know about the theory, and the energy professionals, who want to apply this method in practice.

We would suggest that the latter might be interested in the (partial) implementation of this method provided by our package [27] for the R Programming Environment [33]. We say “partial”, because the software currently estimates the building parameters and the (log-)posterior probability density functions only before or after the ECM installation; it doesn't (yet) carry out the whole analysis before and after. That must still be done “by hand”.

But we plan to improve that software package and recommend that anyone interested should get in touch with the authors listed on that package's website [27].

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The inset map of Switzerland in Fig. 2 is the “Switzerland - Single Color” vector map by FreeVectorMaps.com.

Source code

This paper was prepared with L^AT_EX, exported to the R_nw format, and processed by knitr [34]. The source L^AT_EX file and the generated R_nw file are available from <https://github.com/dlindelof/cartwheel>.

Appendix

A photograph of the original, manual oil level readouts is shown in Fig. 8.

□

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Heizstände Liegenschaft: WE 5114; Sargans

Volumen Tank ~~13470~~ 13470

Datum	Stand Tank 1	Stand Tank 2	Stand Tank 3	Stand Tank 4	Füllungen	Letzte Wartung
3.2.2011	7000L	4200L	4700L			
25.5.2011	5500L	13000				
25.10.11	4000L	13000				
25.11.11	10700L					
23.07.12	10500L	3500L				2009
16.4.12	10000	500				
02.05.12		11100L	10600		Wachspfüllung im Tank 2	
27.05.12	8000	10000L				
15.01.13	10000L	10000L				
15.01.13	10000L	10300L			Tank 1 wird nachgefüllt	
6.03.13	10000L	5200L				
12.6.13	10000L	5000L				
15.8.13	9500L	0000L			3500	12500
16.8.13	12400L	12500L				
27.10.13	13437L	8800L				
25.2.14	10000L	5000L				
25.2.14	89500	5000L				
24.9.14	9000	5000L			Tank 2 empfüllt 12000L	
24.9.14	9000	10500L				
18.11.14	7000	12500L			Tank 1 werden 2000L	
18.11.14	7400	12500L				
03.12.2014	7100	12200				
10.02.15	8100	12100				
25.02.15	0/13200	2500/13000			Tank 2 / A. Nachgefüllt 20423L	13.000
11.06.15	13200	10000			HS	
15.12.15	13200	3500			HS	
8.3.16	8500					

Figure 8: The original manual oil level readouts

Generation in R, URL <https://yihui.name/knitr/>, R package version 1.17, 2017.